

Policing in the Covid-19 Situation in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Since March 2020, Indonesia has entered Covid-19 emergency status. Covid-19 pandemic situation forged various aspects, through social, economic, political, and cultural. This situation places Indonesia in a critical situation which has a great chance of social unrest. Indonesian National Police as the forefront of law enforcement in Indonesia, faces two real consequences: carrying out the main tasks of the police itself and additional tasks to deal with the Covid-19 emergency handling agenda. To support these tasks, Indonesian National Police issued at least 38 (thirty-eight) notice and internal regulation since March to May 2020. Thirteen of those 38 regulations ruled relation between police and community. By analyzing these thirteen regulations, I identified policing implementation in Indonesia. As a result, these thirteen regulations are dominated by points that indicate democratic policing where persuade, coordinate, anticipated, campaigns, encourage, and transparent being methods that mostly used in the enforcement framework. Indonesian National Police's consistency in orienting towards community-based policing shows their commitment in promoting Indonesia values as democratic nation.

KEYWORDS: Covid-19, policy, policing, democratic policing, community-based policing

I. INTRODUCTION

In December 2019, Chinese government announced the spread of a new virus which was later confirmed by the World Health Organization (WHO) and officially named Covid-19. Following this announcement, WHO issued 6 (six) priority strategic issues in efforts to prevent and control Covid-19: deploying all medical personnel, implementing a system that can track suspicious cases, producing and providing mass test kits, identifying facilities that can be temporarily converted into a center for handling Covid-19 patients, drafting plans for quarantine cases, and affirming the focus of government measurements in an effort to reduce the spread of the virus (World Health Organization, 2020). This situation triggered a global response to prevent the mass spread of the virus. Social restrictions, self-quarantine, lockdown, and cessation of various activities and services in public spaces were common practices done in many countries in the world.

As a response to pandemic situation, Indonesian government had also taken several quick steps by issuing several policies that involved various roles of government institutions. One of them is the enactment of Government Regulation Number 6 of 2020 concerning Large-Scale Social Restrictions in the Context of Accelerating Handling of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) which is supported by Regulation of the Minister of Health Number 9 of 2020 concerning Guidelines for Large-Scale Social Restrictions in the Framework of Acceleration Handling of Covid-19. Both set restrictions on certain activities of residents in a situation suspected area of being infected with a disease and/or contaminated in such a way as to prevent wider spread of the virus. Activities that are restricted, include work, school, public transport using, public space meeting, and other activities related to national defense and security.

To support the Large-Scale Social Restrictions Regulation (LSSRR), Indonesian National Police imposed various new regulations as adjustment to the Covid-19 pandemic situation. These policies consist of the support regulations for policies issued by health agencies that act as the frontline for the prevention of Covid-19 to policies that have implications for law enforcement. This paper explains policies that were issued by Indonesian National Police during the Covid-19 situation in Indonesia and how its implementation in the policing framework analysis.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a desk research study which use database of regulations released by Indonesia National Police during March-May 2020. Data were divided into four categories of regulation: regulation related to virus spread prevention, police duties, implementing and coordination tasks, and administration of internal police institutions. The policy analysis was then carried out to see the trend of policing which was represented in the form of regulation in which there was interaction between the Police and

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the community related to the maintenance of public order, prevention of crime, and law enforcement imposed by the police during the pandemic by referring to indicators of democratic policing and conventional policing.

III. INDONESIAN NATIONAL POLICE POLICIES IN RESPONSE TO THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC SITUATION

Since the first case of Covid-19 was announced in early March to May 2020, Indonesian National Police has imposed at least 38 (thirty-eight) new regulations to adjust to the Covid-19 emergency situation. These regulations were issued in the form of Chief of Police Notices, Secret Telegrams (STR), and Telegrams (ST).

In contrast to Indonesian National Police Notice which is an official appeal addressed to the public, Telegram is an internal order letter addressed to the internal body of Indonesian National Police throughout Indonesia to serve as a guide in carrying out their duties and functions. Even though it is for internal purposes, some of these Telegrams can also be published openly by the Police and known to the public.

In general, the regulations refer to Minister of Health Regulation No. 9 of 2020, which outlines the role of the Indonesian National Police in dealing with the Covid-19 situation, namely:

1. Centralized and regional police operations.
2. Police activities carried out by the police force to support the Task Force for the Acceleration of Handling Covid-19, both at the national level and at the provincial/district/city level.
3. Police routine activities to ensure public security and order.

In particular, the three roles refer to support activities in the form of limiting public activities, guarding regional borders, regulating public transportation, and maintaining security and order as the main duties of the police.

These regulations can be divided into 4 (four) category magnitudes. First, preventing the spread of the virus which regulating the role of Indonesian National Police in preventing the spread of Covid-19 in the community. Second, the implementation of the police's duties which regulating the implementation of the duties of maintaining public order, preventing crime, and enforcing the law to create a sense of security in the community. Third, the implementation of coordination tasks which coordinating activities with various parties to help prevent and control the spread of Covid-19 successfully. Last, the implementation of regulations related to the internal administration and order of Indonesian National Police to prevent the spread of Covid-19 in their internal environment.

To enforce these regulations, Indonesian National Police formed a Special Task Force namely Aman Nusa II which is led by the Head of the Police Security Maintenance Agency. The commander of this Task Force is also act a Indonesian National Police's representative in coordinating with other agencies in Indonesian Task Force for the Acceleration of Covid-19 Handling.

Aman Nusa II has three sub-task forces, each of which has a special task. First, the General Crime Sub-Task Force for handling conventional crimes such as theft, looting, robbery, crime during natural disasters, and violations of health quarantine protocols. Second, the Economic Sub-Task Force to supervise and take action against food and medical stuff hoarding, against exporters of antiseptics, raw materials for masks, personal protective equipment (PPE), and masks. This task force also takes action against drugs or medical devices that do not comply with standards/ distribution permits. Last, the Cyber Sub-Task Force in charge of prosecuting Covid-19 hoaxes, provocateurs related to Covid-19 through online media, and online fraud related to sale of medical devices.

IV. POLICING CHALLENGES IN THE COVID-19 EMERGENCY SITUATION

There are two major government agendas during this pandemic: fighting Covid-19 and the economic crisis (Djalante et al., 2020). As a result, policing in the midst of an emergency situation for the Covid-19 pandemic is a real challenge for law enforcement officials such as Indonesian National Police, who are at the forefront of the criminal justice system in Indonesia. Indonesian National Police faced an emergency of the spread of an outbreak which in this case has the consequence of carrying out dual duties, the main duties of the police themselves and additional tasks in order to face the agenda for handling the emergency situation of Covid-19.

Article 5 of Law Number 2 of 2002 concerning the State Police of the Republic of Indonesia states that Indonesian National Police as an instrument of the state plays a role in maintaining public security and order, enforcing the law, as well as providing protection and services to the community in the framework of maintaining domestic security. Facing this pandemic situation, Indonesian National Police is also required to be responsible for carrying out Indonesian National Police's duties, especially those related to maintaining domestic security as a result of the pandemic situation, such as: enforcing regulations to maintain public compliance during Large-Scale Social Restrictions (LSSRR), coordinating with Covid-19 Management Task Force, and support for prevention and control measures for the spread of Covid-19 in the community,

A pandemic situation that forces people to adapt to various limitations creates a great opportunity for social unrest. Restrictions on activities as a consequence of the implementation of LSSRR have made the community experience various critical situations, such as loss of sources of income due to a decline in sectors such: as aviation, tourism, hotels, restaurants, shipping and transportation, as well as other derivative sectors; limited access to medical services and public services; disruption of educational

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and teaching activities; increasing cases of domestic violence, mental health disorders; injustice; and other adverse consequences (Djalante et al., 2020). Furthermore, most people in the community have lack of understanding or awareness towards the risk of Covid-19. This situation made them neglecting rules or procedures to prevent Covid-19 transmission, thus endanger others (Djalante et al., 2020; Fachriansyah et al., 2020).

On the other hand, risks also arise when law enforcement cannot be carried out normally. The criminal justice system does not function normally. Detention must consider the limited space for detention/capacity of detention centers and prisons. Also, trial process can only be held online. The impact of this law enforcement situation can be seen from the increasing number of crimes in the community as noted by Indonesian National Police:

Figure 1. Criminal Statistic in Indonesia, January-March 2020 (Criminal Investigation Agency of the Indonesian National Police, 2020).

The crime rate data shows that although February saw a decrease in the number of conventional crimes, transnational crimes, contingent crimes and crimes against state property, this condition did not last long. With the exception of contingent crimes, there was a jump in the number of each type of crime simultaneously in March, when Covid-19 had started spreading in Indonesia.

The government through the Ministry of Law and Human Rights has also implemented a policy of early release for 38,822 prisoners through the application of reintegration rights, such as assimilation, parole, and conditional leave (Investigation Agency of Indonesian National Police, 2020; Sudaryono, 2020). Although the implementation of the policy is good and is not a definite predictor variable for the number of crimes during the pandemic, the adoption of this policy has created fear of crime in the community, especially with excessive media coverage (Nugroho et al., 2020; Prabowo, 2020).

As a result, social unrest has a greater chance of occurring in society. Stott et al. (2020) explained that social unrest has a large correlation with a sense of public dissatisfaction. The feeling of dissatisfaction shown can give birth to social unrest (Stott et al., 2020). Regarding to this statement, the case of George Floyd's death which escalated into a case of rioting and looting in several states in the United States can be the most obvious example of social unrest that has occurred due to the current pandemic situation. The insistent injustice felt by black groups, especially during the pandemic, made George Floyd's case like a gun lighter with a big explosion (BBC News, 2020).

In this critical situation, various adjustments to policing practices with efforts to prevent and control the spread of Covid-19 have led to shifts of the type of policing application. It is a critical point of policing, as is the case in all countries facing the problem of the spread of Covid-19 (Luscombe & McClelland, 2020; Stott et al., 2020). Therefore, in this situation, the policies issued and how they are implemented are the key to the successful implementation of police duties and functions.

V. INDONESIAN POLICING IN THE ERA OF PANDEMIC COVID-19: DEMOCRATIC OR CONVENTIONAL?

The history of the development of policing recognizes at least two category of policing: conventional policing and democratic policing. The distinction between the two can be clearly identified from the relationship that is built between the police and community in carrying out police duties.

Conventional policing tends to see the relationship between police and community in a superior and inferior position, subject and object, or ordinate and sub ordinate where both are in unequal positions. In this case, the police position themselves as law enforcement officers, are repressive, based on legal theory, and are therapeutic in nature. On the other side, democratic policing sees community as partners who can work together with the police in prevention and law enforcement efforts. The characteristics of this policing are that community takes part in exercising social control (self-help), is humanistic, based on the theory of altruism, and is constitutional in nature. In civilian policing, the success of policing is not measured by how many people are detained, processed, and sent to prison (Rahardjo, 2005).

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Facing a pandemic situation, various forms of policing are changing as a form of adjustment. It is not uncommon for democratic policing that has been implemented before to shift to more conventional policing in a tense situation like today. From various research results reviewed by Stott, et al. (2020), there is a general conclusion regarding the success of policing practices in this pandemic situation, namely that the police institution needs to build a strategic approach and a policing model that facilitates public needs and the implementation of Indonesian National Police's duties and powers by prioritizing the principles of justice, proportionality, respect for human rights, and legitimacy.

The new social contract that was formed from the Covid-19 pandemic situation needs to position the public to be able to understand that these policies were made in response to efforts to protect public health as well as to protect the community itself as a whole.

"A narrowly 'securitized' approach - one that is seen solely as an expression of state power - could erode trust in policing and in government. But if the state and police are seen to protect collective security — against both the epidemic and the consequences of the disruption resulting from it — this would present a significant opportunity to nurture and reconstruct the fundamental principle of policing by consent (Stott et al., 2020)."

In this view, Stott et al. (2020) at least hinted that conventional policing is still possible even though it has negative consequences for public trust in the police. Collective policing is still better to do as a capital to build the principle of policing by consent or policing that places the police and society in an equal relationship and cooperate and support each other in maintaining security and order.

The adjustment of policing practices that occurred as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia can be identified from the formulation of the regulations in response to Covid-19 situation. The stronger the intention to demonstrate the authority of the police institution, the more cruel and disturbing the punishments made as a consequence of violating these rules (Stott et al., 2020). The more repressive, the policing practice will be further away from the community-oriented policing model.

Then what is the policing style represented by the policies that have been passed by the Indonesian National Police during this pandemic? From the categorization results as shown above, there are at least 13 (thirteen) regulations that involve the community as the target for their implementation.

Of the 13 (thirteen) existing regulations, there are 44 (forty four) points that pertain to the relationship between the Police and the community in the context of preventing the spread of Covid-19 and regulations relating to the implementation of police duties during this pandemic. Of the total 44 points, only 5 (five) points from three different regulations that state strict criminal sanctions/sanctions in accordance with applicable laws and regulations are mentioned as threats of punishment. For the rest, the Police use pre-emptive and preventive measures to maintain security and order during this pandemic as can be seen below:

Figure 2. An overview of the interaction between police and community in the regulations related to preventing the spread of Covid-19.

Pre-emptive and preventive measures can be identified by the method chosen to be used/determined in carrying out Indonesian National Police's duties. From 44 points of 13 rules above, these methods are dominated by: persuade, coordinate, anticipated,

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campaigns, encourage, and transparent. These methods see the community as a partner where the community takes part in exercising social control (self help), are humanistic, altruistic, and consistent as stated by Rahardjo (2005).

VI. CONCLUSION

Although it may not be perfect, the response of Indonesian National Police members in security efforts during the Covid-19 emergency situation has shown a positive sign. Indonesian National Police prioritizes dialogue rather than stiff punishment. Indonesian National Police also prioritizes prevention efforts over crime control. This indicates that the Police, through both regulation and implementation, is adhering to democratic policing.

VII. DISCUSSION

The history of Indonesian policing has progressed from colonial policing to policing that prioritizes the values of independence (Rahardjo, 2005). Democratic policing as reflected in the above regulations has shown how Indonesian National Police has consistently upheld its commitment to carry out community-based policing as confirmed in Regulation of the Chief of Indonesian National Police of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2015 concerning Community Policing.

However, the relationship between the police and society will only be positively formed when justice is properly distributed between the two (Sunshine & Tyler, 2003). The distributive justice that is tried to be realized in community-based policing needs to be proven, not only in regulations, but also in its implementation in the field. In the context of the Covid-19 emergency response action, this implementation can at least be seen from how the Police response at the beginning of Covid-19 entered Indonesia and after 38 (thirty eight) Indonesian National Police regulations related to the prevention and handling of the spread of Covid-19 were released.

Regarding to this, I identify the implementation of the problem-oriented policing (POP) approach in the practice of democratic policing by the Police. In simple terms, POP can be understood as a form of policing which is designed based on the conclusion of the analysis of the phenomenon of crime that occurs in society and how the policing involves the community and its agents as part of the solution to the problem.

Referring to Scott and Clarke's (2020), POP as proposed by Goldstein (2001) can be understood as a policing approach with the following characteristics: 1) inherent in the realm of police duties; 2) based on the results of the analysis/assessment to produce conclusions; 3) conclusions are used as a basis for designing effective strategies in overcoming problems; 4) prioritizing natural prevention efforts; 5) prioritizing the mechanism for handling problems without involving the formal criminal justice system; 6) involving key agencies, the public, and the private sector, as well as other actors who can contribute to solving the problem; 7) encouraging commitment to implementing new strategies; 8) measure the effectiveness of strategy implementation; 9) compiling the measurement results into a report;

As explained, the Indonesian National Police responded to the Covid-19 pandemic situation by releasing the Chief of Police Declaration and implementing regulations related to prevention and crime control. In this case, the Indonesian National Police refers to the rules that have been deployed before. Community involvement is also formulated as a partner in socializing the risk of Covid-19 as formulated in the instructions of the Indonesian National Police Chief to collaborate with key actors in society (SPRIPIM Polri, 2020).

Democratic policing with the POP approach then continues to implement the above rules. In general, the Indonesian National Police is faced with challenges in the form of violating regulations in implementing Large-Scale Social Restrictions (LSSR). Some of the prominent incidents regarding this matter that I noted include: the tension between the community and members of the Indonesian National Police regarding the use of places of worship, homecoming (culture), to rejection of the bodies of Covid-19 victims.

In Bandung, tensions arose when the Bandung Grand Mosque was closed for public worship. A number of community groups came and showed resistance. However, this was handled well with dialogue by the Bandung Police, so that understanding and agreement was reached between related parties (Kurniawan, 2020). Furthermore, the moment of the spread of Covid-19 was also through the homecoming period in Indonesia just before the Eid Al-Fitr. The guard at the moment of the Eid homecoming also succeeded in driving away the travelers peacefully. At least, the Indonesian National Police managed to block 68,946 vehicles that wanted to join homecoming culture (Burhan, 2020) in various modes during Ketupat operation, such as using an ambulance, vehicles loaded with logistical goods, to vehicles that were exempted from the Large-Scale Social Restriction (LSSR) ban (Lukihardianti, 2020). Furthermore, rejection of the burial of Covid-19's bodies occurred in several areas, such as Central Java and West Sumatra (Gunadha, 2020; "One Corona Patient Body Was Rejected in Padang," 2020). Although it sparked public outrage in cyberspace (Gunadha, 2020), this turmoil did not transform into the real world. The problem solving was successfully carried out by deliberation, without any parties being processed through the criminal justice system.

The above events at least show the characteristics of the problem-oriented policing of the Indonesian National Police in law enforcement during the Covid-19 pandemic. First, the implementation of Indonesian National Police's duties is loaded with situation predictions, so that strategies are taken based on the inferences of the problems obtained from previous experiences. For

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example, the efforts of several community groups to keep trying to worship at the mosque or various tactics carried out by the community to keep homecoming culture. Such community behavior has been predicted by the Police, so Indonesian National Police members are assigned to guard the mosques to open dialogue as a form of prevention, as well as harassment at the pilgrimage points of travelers. These two ways are one of the strategies that are able to keep the situation conducive.

Another characteristic that stands out is that there is an effort to open dialogue as a priority for handling problems, rather than involving the criminal justice system. This practice is found, both in coordination and in maintaining public order. For example, the Indonesian National Police chooses to have a dialogue with the community when people insist on praying at the mosque. Dialogue is also prioritized with key community figures, such as religious leaders to traders of basic necessities, as well as patients with positive identification of Covid-19 who refuse to be picked up by paramedics.

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Table 1. Regulations released by Polri in response to the Covid-19 situation in Indonesia (March-May 2020)

No.	Regulations	Keynote
Virus Spread Prevention		
1	Maklumat Kapolri Nomor: MAK/2/III/2020 tentang Kepatuhan Terhadap Kebijakan Pemerintah dalam Penanganan Penyebaran Virus Corona (Covid-19) (Chief of Police Declaration Number: MAK/2/III/2020 concerning Compliance with Government Policies in Handling the Spread of the Corona Virus (Covid-19))	Public not to hold activities that result public gathering.
2	STR Kapolri Nomor: STR/122/III/PAM.3./2020 tentang Bijak Kapolri Terkait Perkembangan Situasi Akibat Wabah Virus Covid 19 (National Police STR Number: STR/122/III/PAM.3./2020 concerning the National Police Chief Policy Regarding the Development of the Situation Due to the Covid 19 Outbreak)	Arrange for each regional police to prepare 50 to 100 personnel trained by Brimob for spraying disinfectants.
3	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/983/III/OPS.4.5./2020 tentang Arahan Kepada Jajaran Binmas, Samapta, Pamobvit, dan Polairud untuk Melakukan Himbauan Kepada Masyarakat Terkait Penyebaran Virus Covid 19 (ST Kapolri Number: ST/983/III/OPS.4.5./2020 concerning Directions to ranks of the Binmas, Samapta, Pamobvit, and Polairud to appeal to Public Regarding the Spread of the Covid Virus 19)	Regulating orders to carry out appeals to the public regarding the spread of the corona virus in the ranks of Binmas, Samapta, Pamobvit and Polairud.
4	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1002/III/KEP/2020 tentang Arahan Kepada Jajaran Lantas untuk Melaksanakan Protokol Kesehatan di Area Yan Publik (ST Kapolri Number: ST/1002/III/KEP/2020 concerning Directives to the Next Line for Implementing Health Protocols in Public Service Areas)	Set directions for implementing health protocols in public service areas.

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5	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1031/III/OPS.4.3./2020 tentang Arahan Kepada Dir Binmas Untuk Sosialisasi Kepada Masyarakat Terkait Penyebaran Virus Covid 19 (ST Kapolri Number: ST/1031/III/OPS.4.3./2020 concerning Directions to Director of Binmas for Socialization to the Public Regarding the Spread of the Covid Virus 19)	Directive to Director of Binmas ranks about directions for carrying out outreach the spread of Covid-19 to the public.
<hr/> Implementation of Police Duties <hr/>		
1	ST/766/III/OPS.4.5./2020 tentang Himbauan Untuk Tidak Panic Buying (ST/766/III/OPS.4.5./2020 concerning Appeals Not to Panic Buying)	Directive to Dirbinmas regional police ranks to carry out appeal activities and face to face with the community.
2	ST/884/III/KES.2/2020 tentang Giat Preventif Fungsi Kepolisian di Area Penyimpanan Maupun Penjualan Sembako (ST/884/III/KES.2/2020 concerning Active Preventive Functions of the Police in the Area of Storage and Sales of Groceries)	Regulate about active preventive monitoring of the availability and sales of groceries.
3	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/900/III/HUM.1.1./2020 tentang Giat Preventif Dampak Negatif Terkait Virus Covid 19 (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/900/III/HUM.1.1./2020 concerning Active Preventive Negative Impacts Related to the Covid 19 Virus)	The directive to Director of Sabhara to increases police activities in the preventive field.
4	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1007/III/HUK.5./2020 tentang Jukrah Penanganan Tindak Pidana Umum Selama Masa Pencegahan Penyebaran Virus Covid 19 (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1007/III/HUK.5./2020 concerning Jukrah Handling General Crimes During the Prevention Period of the Spread of the Covid 19 Virus)	Set about the direction of follow-up in handling general crimes during the prevention of the spread of the corona virus.
5	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1009/III/OPS.2./2020 tentang Pelaksanaan Opsus Kontijensi Covid 19 Aman Nusa II (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1009/III/OPS.2./2020 concerning Implementation of Covid 19 Safe Opsus Contingency Nusa II)	Regulates the implementation of the Special Operations for the Safe Covid-19 Contingency Nusa II.
6	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1042/III/KEP./2020 tentang <i>Smart Policing</i> (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1042/III/KEP./2020 concerning Smart Policing)	Directive to Kapolda to implement Smart Policing measures during the Covid-19 Pandemic

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7	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1098/IV/HUK.7.1./2020 tentang Jukrah Penanganan Perkara Kejahatan dalam Masa PSBB (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1098/IV/HUK.7.1./2020 concerning Jukrah Handling Crime Cases in the PSBB Period)	Regulates guidelines for carrying out duties during the period of preventing the spread of the corona virus in handling criminal cases during the Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) period.
8	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1100/IV/HUK.7.1./2020 tentang Jukrah Penanganan Tindak Pidana Siber (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1100/IV/HUK.7.1./2020 concerning about direction in handling cybercrime)	Set about the direction of follow-up handling cybercrime during spread prevention of corona virus.
9	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1099/IV/HUK.7.1./2020 tentang Ketersediaan Bahan Pokok (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1099/IV/HUK.7.1./2020 concerning the Availability of Basic Goods)	Regulate the handling of cases and guidelines for the implementation of the duties of the criminal investigations function related to the availability and distribution process of staple goods
Implementation of Coordination Tasks		
1	STR Kapolri Nomor: STR/121/III/PAM.3./2020 tentang Direktif Kegiatan Kerja Bakti secara Masif Berkaitan dengan Wabah Virus Covid-19 (STR Kapolri Nomor: STR/121/III/PAM.3./2020 concerning Massive Community Service Activities Directive Related to the Covid-19 Virus Outbreak)	Arrange for coordination and cooperation with the Provincial Health Office, Regional Disaster Management Agency, and local stakeholders.
2	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/942/III/OPS.1.2./2020 tentang Arahan Untuk Membentuk Tim Satgas Covid 19 Biddokes Polda Jajaran (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/942/III/OPS.1.2./2020 regarding Directions for Forming the Covid 19 Medicine and Health Team in regional police)	Arranging orders to form a Covid-19 task force team to the Regional Police Chief through Chief of Medicine and Health division.
3	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/972/III/KEP./2020 tentang Vicon PJU Biddokes dan Karumkit Bhayangkara dalam Rangka Pemberdayaan Rumkit Bhayangkara sebagai Tempat Perawatan PDP Covid 19 (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/972/III/KEP./2020 concerning Vicon PJU Biddokes and Karumkit Bhayangkara in the Context of Empowering Bhayangkara Health Center as a Treatment Place for patients under monitoring of Covid 19)	Regulating the implementation of the OJU Dokkes vicon in the context of empowering Bhayangkara health care as a treatment area for the patients under monitoring of corona virus
4	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1003/III/IPP.2./2020 tentang Jukrah Kepada Jajaran Intelkam Monitoring Terkait Penyebaran Virus Covid 19 (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1003/III/IPP.2./2020 concerning Direction to the Intelligence and Security Team for Monitoring Regarding the Spread of the Covid 19 Virus)	Arranging directions for carrying out coordination with related institutions to maintain supply and demand as well as monitoring products and raw materials

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5	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1004/III/IPP.2./2020 tentang Arahan Jajaran Intelkam Monitoring Dampak Ekonomi Pandemi Virus Covid 19</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1004/III/IPP.2./2020 concerning the Direction of the Intelligence Unit for Monitoring the Economic Impact of the Covid Virus Pandemic 19)</p>	<p>Directive to Dirintelkam to monitor companies that may be affected by the decline in the composite stock price index and foreign capital which could harm the public and have the potential to interrupt our social and security services.</p>
Administrative Rules/Internal Rules		
1	<p>STR Kapolri Nomor: STR/159/IV/OPS.4./2020 tentang Penggunaan Pakaian PDL II Two Tone Lengan Baju Tanpa Dilipat</p> <p>(STR Kapolri Nomor: STR/159/IV/OPS.4./2020 concerning uniform rules during Covid-19 situation)</p>	<p>Regulate uniform usage procedures during Aman Nusa II operation or Covid-19 situation.</p>
2	<p>ST/868/III/KEP./2020 tentang Antisipasi Virus Covid-19</p> <p>(ST/868/III/KEP./2020 concerning anticipation of the Covid-19)</p>	<p>Regulate activities to support the program to maintain body health (using masks, hand sanitizers, and shaking procedures).</p>
3	<p>ST/872/III/KEP./2020 tentang Pembatasan Kegiatan yang Melibatkan Banyak Orang</p> <p>(ST/872/III/KEP./2020 concerning Limitation of Activities That Involve Many People)</p>	<p>Regulates the postponement of official program activities involving members of the National Police and public service officer of Indonesia National Police.</p>
4	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/889/III/BIN.1.1./2020 tentang Arahan untuk Menjaga Kebersihan Tempat Ibadah di Lingkungan Polri</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/889/III/BIN.1.1./2020 concerning Directions for Maintaining the Cleanliness of Places of Worship in the Police Environment)</p>	<p>Regulate the steps in active religious guidance/service of the Police</p>
5	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/895/III/KEP./2020 tentang Arahan Kepada Jajaran Lantas Untuk Antisipasi Penyebaran Covid-19</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/895/III/KEP./2020 Directives to the traffic police department to Anticipate the Spread of Covid-19)</p>	<p>Directive to the Director of traffic regional police ranks to maintain physical fitness and cleanliness in carrying out services to the community.</p>
6	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/940/III/BIN.1.1./2020 tentang Penundaan Ibadah di Tempat Ibadah di Lingkungan Polri</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/940/III/BIN.1.1./2020 concerning Postponement of Worship at Places of Worship in the Police Environment)</p>	<p>Regulates the suspension of congregational worship activities for civil servants at the police office area.</p>
7	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/941/KEP./2020 tentang Work From Home Bagi PNS Polri</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/941/KEP./2020 concerning work from home for public civil servant of Indonesia National Police)</p>	<p>Arranging the implementation of official duties at his home/residence in turn.</p>

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8	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/965/III/KEP./2020 tentang Arahan Untuk Menunda Kegiatan Resepsi/Pesta yang Diselenggarakan oleh Anggota Maupun PNS Polri Guna Menghindari Perkumpulan Massa</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/965/III/KEP./2020 concerning Directions for Delaying Reception/ Party Activities Organized by Members and Civil Servants of the National Police to Avoid the public gathering)</p>	Regulate directives for non-action / enterprising that are counter-productive to joint efforts to prevent the spread corona virus
9	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/968/III/RES.10.1./2020 tentang Penundaan Pelaksanaan Binkatpuan Penyidik PPNS</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/968/III/RES.10.1./2020 concerning Postponement of the formation and appointment of Police civil servant investigators)</p>	Regulates the postponement of the implementation of Police civil servant investigators' notes
10	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1001/III/KEP./2020 tentang Jukrah Jajaran Lantas Menyediakan Sarana untuk Antisipasi Penyebaran Virus Covid 19</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1001/III/KEP./2020 concerning directive traffic police department to Provides Materials to Anticipate the Spread of the Covid 19 Virus)</p>	Arranging directives for the traffic police department to provide a means to anticipate the spread of the Covid 19 virus
11	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1083/IV/KEP./2020 tentang Imbauan Bagi Anggota dan PNS Polri Beserta Keluarganya Untuk Tidak Berpergian</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1083/IV/KEP./2020 concerning Appeals for Police Members and Civil Servants and Their Families Not to Travel)</p>	Orders to members of the National Police and PNS Polri not to travel outside the region and or homecoming activities
12	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1097/IV/HUK.7.1./2020 tentang Jukrah Pedoman Pelaksanaan Tugas Fungsi Reskrim</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1097/IV/HUK.7.1./2020 concerning directive Guidelines for the Implementation of Criminal Investigation Functions)</p>	Regulate the handling of cases and guidelines for implementing the duties of criminal investigations related to state apparatus involved in handling Covid-19
13	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1101/IV/HK.7.1/2020 tentang Jukrah Pedoman Pelaksanaan Tugas Fungsi Reksrim</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1101/IV/HK.7.1/2020 concerning Guidelines for Implementation of Tasks Reksrim function)</p>	Regulates guidelines for implementing the duties of the criminal investigative function related to the need for personal protective equipment (PPE)
14	<p>ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1102/IV/HUK.7.1/2020 tentang Jukrah Pedoman Pelaksanaan Tugas Fungsi Reksrim</p> <p>(ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1101/IV/HK.7.1/2020 concerning Guidelines for Implementation of Tasks Reksrim function)</p>	Set about run command health handling procedures by sea, air, land, airport, and traffic land border of the country

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15	Surat B/2251/IV/KEP./2020/PUSDOKKES Tanggal 1 April 2020 tentang Protokol Isolasi Mandiri (Surat Kapolri B/2251/IV/KEP./2020/PUSDOKKE Tanggal 1 April 2020 concerning Self-Isolation Protocol)	Nomor: Nomor:	Orders to disseminate self-isolation protocols for handling Covid-19 to the Head of Health, Health, Safety, and Security of the Police, the Head of the Pusdokkes Polri, Kabiddokes Polda and Kapoliklinik Polri
16	ST Kapolri Nomor: 1008/III/KES.7./2020 tentang Arahan Kepada Jajaran Untuk Melakukan Gerakan Masif Penyemprotan Cairan Disinfektan (ST Kapolri Nomor: 1008/III/KES.7./2020 concerning Directions to Staff to Carry out Massive Movement of Spraying Disinfectant Liquid)		Regulates the implementation of disinfectant spraying in the context of preventing the simultaneous spread of the corona virus
17	STR Kapolri Nomor: STR/80/II/PAM.3./2020 tentang Jukrah Menyikapi Peredaran Virus Covid-19 (STR Kapolri Nomor: STR/80/II/PAM.3./2020 concerning directive in Responding to the Circulation of the Covid-19 Virus)		Regulates the steps that must be taken by all levels to make the Sitkamtibmas stay conducive
18	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1041/III/KEP./2020 tentang Arahan Jajaran Lantas dalam Standar Penanganan Korban Laka sebagai Antisipasi Penularan Virus Covid 19 (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/1041/III/KEP./2020 concerning Direct Line Directives in the Standard for Handling of Traffic Accident Victims as Anticipation of Covid 19 Virus Transmission)		Regulating the standard operating procedur and then in the standard of handling victims of victim street accident in anticipation of the transmission of the Covid 19 virus
19	ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/909/III/YAN.1.2./2020 tentang Langkah Antisipatif Penyebaran Virus Covid 19 Pada Layanan Bidang Lantas (SIM/STNK) (ST Kapolri Nomor: ST/909/III/YAN.1.2./2020 concerning Anticipatory Steps for the Spread of the Covid 19 Virus in the Services Field of Unit of Traffic (Driver Lisence /Vehicle Registration))		Regulates steps to anticipate the spread of the Covid-19 virus in units of the National Police, especially those services for driving lisence and vehicle registration.